

USE OF COMPOSITE SOLVENTS IN THE EXTRACTION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This study developed a technology for producing a high-protein, safe product for the food and feed industries by reducing the gossypol content in cottonseed cake. The aim of the study was to neutralize gossypol and maximize protein content through an extraction process. Physicochemical methods, solvent selection, determination of optimal parameters, and cottonseed cake quality assessment were used. The results suggest innovative approaches to increasing the efficiency of gossypol removal and preserving protein.

Since the chemical composition of substances differs from each other, the solvents used to separate them using solvents are also different. Extraction of components from raw materials using solvents is an extraction process and is widely used in various industries. The correct choice of solvents significantly increases the efficiency of the extraction process and ensures high quality of the product obtained [1, 2].

To date, organic solvents, in particular ethanol, hexane, acetone, aromatic hydrocarbons, alcohols such as methanol, and petroleum fractions, are widely used in the extraction process [3, 4]. Extraction is one of the main processes in the production of vegetable oils, and organic solvents such as N-hexane, nefras, and extraction gasoline are used [5-7].

Direct extraction process. Another method of obtaining vegetable oils is the direct extraction method, in which, like the above two methods, the oily raw materials are cleaned, separated from the shell, and after being crushed (crushed) into a leaf-like fraction, they are directly transferred to the extractor device. The extraction process lasts longer than in the forpress extraction method. The separated micelles are sent to the refining plant after the distillation stage [6-7].

At the same time, the correct selection of solvents used in the extraction of oils, the creation of optimal conditions for the extraction process, and the obtaining of high-quality oils are of great importance.

The physical characteristics of some solvent extractants widely used in industry are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Physical properties of extractants used in the extraction process

№	Indicator name	Solvents				
		Isopropanol	Methanol	Ethanol	Acetone	Diethyl ether
1	Relative density of solvents, at a temperature of 15 °C, g/cm ³	0,785	0,792	0,789	0,790	0,714
2	Boiling temperature, °C	82,4	64,7	78,39	56,1	34,65
3	Flight temperature, °C	11,7	6	13	-20	-45
4	Aromatic hydrocarbon quantity, %	0,3	0,1	0,1	0,11	0,4
5	Hazard class	3	3	4	4	3
6	Chemical formula	S ₃ N ₈ O	SN ₄ O	S ₂ N ₆ O	S ₃ N ₆ O	(SN ₃ SN ₂) ₂ O
7	Molar mass, g/mol	60	32	46	58	74,18

As can be seen from Table 1, the boiling points, volatilization temperatures and densities of the extractants used in the extraction process are different, and are selected based on the field of application of the oils obtained using these solvents. The solvents used in the extraction process are divided into 3 classes according to their toxicity and environmental hazard. The solvents with the lowest hazard level are classified as Class 4, the solvents that pose a risk of death are classified as Class 3, and the substances with the highest hazard level are classified as Class 2. Of the solvents listed in the table, 3 belong to Class 3, while 2 belong to Class 4.

Studies have shown that the extraction process is one of the most important processes in the extraction of vegetable oils, and the extractants widely used today require individual selection for each type of oily raw material, depending on the type of oil and the field of use. In industry, the most suitable solvent for the extraction of vegetable oils is extraction gasoline, which is mainly referred to in production technology as "Nefras" or "Extraction gasoline" and is widely used due to its high availability, low cost, and safety compared to other solvents.

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